

Data Management Plan

Machine Learning in agriculture

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Contact person: *There are no contact people define*

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Data Management Plan created in Data Stewardship Wizard <<https://ds-wizard.org>>

Abstract

The idea is a system for the farmer that he can use to monitor his plants without having to go to the field and check for themselves. This is very important for many farmers, because they can save time and use it in other parts to maximize their winnings. We try to get as many pictures of the plants as we can and in as many categories as we can. The categories are pictures of healthy plants, pictures of sick plants, newly planted and fully grown plants. Then we feed them into a Machine Learning system so that this system can learn from these pictures and create a model. Then when everything is set up, we only have to take pictures of the plants on the field (for example with a drone) and send them to the system. The system then categorizes everything and tells the farmer the current status of his plants on the field.

Section A: Data Collection

1. What data will you collect or create?

Instrument datasets

The following instrument datasets will be acquired in the project:

- **Images from plnts on field**

This dataset will be collected by experts in the project, with our own equipment.

The equipment is very well described and known.

Re-used datasets

We will use the following reference datasets:

- **[Plants of the World Online](http://www.plantsoftheworldonline.org)** (<http://www.plantsoftheworldonline.org>)

We will use the following already existing non-reference datasets:

- **[Plants of the World Online](#)**

We will download or get a copy.

Data formats and types

We will be using the following data formats and types:

- **[Portable Network Graphics](#)**

It is a standardized format. This is a suitable format for long-term archiving. We expect to have 1 GB of data in this format.

2. How will the data be collected or created?

Instrument datasets

- **Images from plnts on field**

For this dataset, we are using the following instruments:

- **Drone** – A drone with a camera on it, to take pictures of the whole field and their plants

We will not be using quality process for this dataset.

Storage and file conventions

We will use a filesystem with files and folders with the following folder conventions:

- There will be a **folder for each sample/subject**. Each of those will use the following conventions: Every plant-type gets its own folder. Foldername = Plantname.

Moreover, we have made appointments about naming the files.

We will not be storing data in an "object store" system.

We will not use a relational database system to store project data.

We will not use a graph database for data in the project.

We will not be storing data in a triple store.

Section B: Documentation and Meta-data

3. What documentation and meta-data will accompany the data?

List of data to be published is given in Section E, Question 9. This also includes information about catalogs where the data can be found. Information about data types used is given in Section A, Question 1.

We will use an electronic lab notebook to make sure that there is good provenance of the data analysis.

Section C: Ethics and Legal Compliance

4. How will you manage any ethical issues?

Data we reuse

- [Plants of the World Online](#) does not need an extension of any consent because it is not personal data.

5. How will you manage copyright and Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) issues?

We will be working with the philosophy *as open as possible* for our data.

All of our data can become completely open immediately.

For the reference and non-reference data sets that we reuse, conditions are as follows:

- [Plants of the World Online](#) – freely available for any use (public domain or CC0).

Section D: Storage and Backup

6. How will the data be stored and backed up during the research?

Data that project members themselves store adequately backed up and traceable. Therefore data are protected against both equipment failure and human error.

7. How will you manage access and security?

Project members will not store data or software on computers in the lab or external hard drives connected to those computers. All project web services addressed via secure http (https://...). Project members have been instructed about both generic and specific risks to the project.

The possible impact to the project or organization if information is lost is small.
The possible impact to the project or organization if information is leaked is small.
The possible impact to the project or organization if information is vandalised is small.

We are not using any personal information.

Section E: Selection and Preservation

8. Which data are of long-term value and should be retained, shared, and/or preserved?

We plan to publish the following datasets:

- **Images on plants on the field** – This data set will be kept available as long as technically possible. – The metadata will be available even when the data no longer exists.

9. What is the longterm preservation plan for the dataset?

- **Images on plants on the field** will be stored in our institutional repository.

None of the used repositories charge for their services.

We have a reserved budget for the time and effort it will take to prepare the data for publication.

Section F: Data Sharing

10. How will you share the data?

- **Images on plants on the field** – freely available for any use (public domain or CC0).

Information about used repositories (i.e. where will potential users find out about the data) is provided in Section E, Question 9.

Embargo on the data is described in Section C, Question 5, and Section F, Question 11.

11. Are any restrictions on data sharing required?

Ethical and legal restrictions are documented under Section C. We have used the Data Stewardship Wizard, which made us aware of options to minimize the restrictions.

No data sharing agreement will be required.

Section G: Responsibilities and Resources

12. Who will be responsible for data management?

Markus Janik is responsible for implementing the DMP, and ensuring it is reviewed and revised.

13. What resources will you require to deliver your plan?

To execute the DMP, no additional specialist expertise is required.

We do not require any hardware or software in addition to what is usually available in the institute.

Charges applied by data repositories (if any) are mentioned already in Section E, Question 9.